

The Study of Heart Rate Variability across Different Trimesters of Pregnancy

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Abstract

Background: During pregnancy, changes in heart rate variability (HRV) reflect alterations in the regulation of the autonomic nervous system (ANS). While many previous studies have demonstrated the impact of gestation on ANS control of heart rate in Western populations, this phenomenon is not well understood in the Indian population. Understanding these changes is crucial for insights into maternal autonomic cardiovascular control during normal pregnancy. Our study aimed to analyze cardiac autonomic control throughout different stages of pregnancy using HRV.

Methods: we recorded beat-to-beat variations in SA nodal discharge, recorded by ECG, and were analyzed using HR software to determine the spectral indices of HRV. The assessment occurred between 8:30 AM and 12:00 noon in an isolated examination room. ECG recordings for beat-to-beat heart rate variability analysis were taken after at least 5 minutes of supine rest, with the subjects in a supine position and breathing freely. The ECG was recorded from the precordial leads and transferred online to a microcomputer for HRV analysis. Only stationary time series of approximately 5 minutes, free of arrhythmia and artifacts, were used.

Results: The important findings of this study were that overall heart rate variability, as reflected by time-domain (SDNN, RMSSD, SDDSD) and frequency-domain (VLF, LF, HF) measures, was significantly decreased in pregnant women compared to non-pregnant controls. A reduction in high-frequency (HF) power and an increase in low-frequency (LF) power suggest a shift towards sympathetic dominance during pregnancy. The point-care plot parameters (SD1 and SD2) indicated a reduction in both short-term and long-term heart rate variability in pregnant women.

Conclusion: The analysis of HRV parameters across different pregnancy trimesters and between primiparous and multiparous women reveals significant alterations in autonomic nervous system function. A consistent reduction in HRV measures was observed throughout pregnancy, indicative of a shift towards sympathetic dominance. These findings underscore the physiological adaptations necessary for sustaining pregnancy.

Keywords: Heart Rate Variability, Pregnancy, Primiparous, Multiparous, Autonomic functions.

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Introduction

Pregnancy induces significant adaptive changes in the body, placing a substantial burden on the cardiovascular system [1]. These changes are partly facilitated by alterations in cardiac autonomic control, which, if disrupted, can lead to conditions such as hypertension [2]. Sympathovagal imbalance is recognized during pregnancy [3] and can be assessed through heart rate as a measure of parasympathetic function and blood pressure as a measure of sympathetic function. Heart rate

variability (HRV), a more comprehensive autonomic function test, measures beat-to-beat variation in the RR interval of an electrocardiogram [4]. A healthy heart exhibits high HRV, whereas reduced HRV indicates an increased risk of cardiovascular morbidity [4]. HRV provides a precise and non-invasive method for analyzing autonomic regulation of the cardiovascular system.

In obstetrics, reduced HRV in the fetus is commonly used to identify fetal distress. In

cardiology, HRV has its broadest utility in adults, where reduced HRV indicates decreased parasympathetic and increased sympathetic modulation of heart rate, serving as a predictor of myocardial infarction and congestive heart failure [5]. Additionally, reduced HRV has been repeatedly demonstrated in conditions such as diabetic and alcoholic neuropathies [5]. Cardiac control can be short-term through sympathetic or parasympathetic actions via the MSNA, or long-term through changes in the spinal cord and hypothalamus, leading to alterations in heart rate. Our study aims to analyze HRV parameters in normal pregnant women across different trimesters and explore various related factors.

Material and Methods

This cross-sectional observational study was performed in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, and Physiology in Medical College. The nature of the test was explained to the participants in the vernacular language. The participants were made aware that the test was non-invasive in nature. Written consent was obtained from all the participants of the study. Only those willing to participate in the study were included.

We followed the HRV measurement protocol used in previous studies [6, 7]. Beat-to-beat variations in SA nodal discharge, recorded by ECG, were analyzed using HR software to determine the spectral indices of HRV. The assessment occurred between 8:30 AM and 12:00 noon in an isolated examination room. Patients were instructed to avoid coffee, tea, cola drinks, and smoking for 12 hours, before the procedure. ECG recordings for beat-to-beat heart rate variability analysis were taken after at least 5 minutes of supine rest, with the subjects in a supine position and breathing freely. The ECG was recorded from the precordial leads and transferred online to a microcomputer for HRV analysis. Only stationary time series of approximately 5 minutes duration, free of arrhythmia and artifacts, were used.

HRV Parameters: HRV was analyzed in detail concerning the frequency domain, time domain, and Poincare plot parameters.

Time-Domain Analysis:

- RR interval
- The standard deviation of all RR intervals (SDNN)
- The square root of the mean of the sum of the squares of differences between adjacent RR intervals (RMSSD)
- The standard deviation of successive differences (SDSD)

- pNN50, the percentage of consecutive RR intervals that differ by more than 50 ms.

Frequency-Domain Analysis:

- Power of high-frequency (HF, 0.15–0.40 Hz)
- Low-frequency (LF, 0.04–0.15 Hz)
- Very low-frequency (VLF, below 0.04 Hz) ranges
- LF and HF were also presented in normalized units and as a ratio.

Poincare Plot Analysis:

- SD1 and SD2, standard deviations of the RR interval along the minor and major axes, respectively
- Scatter index, expressed as the ratio of SD1 to SD2, reflecting non-linear HRV.

Statistical analysis: All the available data was uploaded to an MS Excel spreadsheet and analyzed by SPSS version 21 in Windows format. The continuous variables were represented as mean, standard deviation, and percentages. The categorical variables were assessed by the differences in the distribution of various parameters using the ANOVA followed by a post hoc test for quantitative data, and the Chi-square test for qualitative data. The P-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 60 cases with 20 cases each in the first, second, and third trimester were included in the study. A sample of 20 nonpregnant age-matched females were included as controls. Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of participants included in an HRV analysis. Age and height showed minimal differences across groups, with no statistically significant difference (p-value > 0.05). Weight and BMI gradually increased from the first to the third trimester, with statistically significant differences (p-value < 0.05). Hemoglobin levels showed a slight decrease in the third trimester compared to other groups, but the difference was not statistically significant (p-value > 0.05). The ANOVA test indicates significant differences in weight (p = 0.022) and BMI (p = 0.003) across the groups, suggesting that these factors are influenced by pregnancy progression. The results suggest that pregnancy is associated with weight gain and increased BMI, which is expected due to fetal growth and maternal physiological changes. While there were trends in age, height, and hemoglobin levels, these differences were not statistically significant.

Table 1: Demographic profile of cases included in the HRV study

	Frequency	Age (years)	Height in cms	Weight in Kgs	BMI Kg/m ²	Hb gm/dl	Primi/Multi
First trimester	20	26.54 ± 5.5	155.57 ± 8.84	59.5 ± 4.9	23.89 ± 0.57	11.25 ± 0.54	12/8
Second Trimester	20	28.25 ± 3.54	156.19 ± 7.69	58.7 ± 5.5	24.67 ± 0.62	11.54 ± 0.60	13/7
Third Trimester	20	29.05 ± 4.5	154.67 ± 6.48	60.3 ± 5.54	24.91 ± 0.66	10.29 ± 0.72	14/6
Controls (Non-Pregnant)	20	26.28 ± 4.0	154.93 ± 6.99	55.5 ± 4.98	23.48 ± 0.89	11.54 ± 0.80	--
ANOVA	=	0.54	0.04	0.022	0.003	0.45	0.9

Table 2 presents frequency domain parameters of heart rate variability (HRV) analysis across four groups. *VLF (Very Low Frequency)*: There is a significant difference in VLF between the groups ($p = 0.041$), suggesting changes in the ultra-low frequency components of HRV across pregnancy stages and non-pregnant controls. *LF (Low Frequency)*: A significant difference is observed in LF ($p = 0.001$), indicating changes in the sympathetic nervous system activity during pregnancy. *HF (High Frequency)*: Similar to LF, HF also shows significant differences ($p = 0.001$), reflecting alterations in parasympathetic activity across the groups. *LF/HF Ratio*: The LF/HF ratio, an indicator of sympathovagal balance, is

significantly different across groups ($p = 0.0215$), suggesting changes in autonomic nervous system modulation during pregnancy. *Heart Rate*: While there seems to be an increase in heart rate in the third trimester compared to other groups, the difference is not statistically significant ($p = 0.06$). *Mode Value*: There is a significant difference in mode value ($p = 0.012$), indicating variations in the most frequent R-R interval across groups. The increases in LF and decreases in HF indicate a shift towards sympathetic dominance during pregnancy. The changes in VLF and mode value might reflect alterations in other physiological processes related to pregnancy.

Table 2: Frequency domain parameters of HRV analysis in different groups

Parameters	First trimester	Second trimester	Third trimester	Controls	P value
VLF	1120.29 ± 753.06	1121.33 ± 1120.3	1098.43 ± 1019.34	1921.91 ± 1837.2	0.041*
LF (nu)	0.303 ± 0.19	0.350 ± 0.13	0.293 ± 0.13	0.491 ± 0.25	0.001*
HF(nu)	0.70 ± 0.28	0.70 ± 0.14	0.69 ± 0.17	0.471 ± 0.27	0.001*
LF: HF Ratio	0.62 ± 0.44	0.84 ± 0.95	0.70 ± 0.87	2.12 ± 4.09	0.0215*
Heart rate	90.5 ± 12.35	92.55 ± 27.52	115.4 ± 37.61	99.17 ± 57.91	0.06
Mode Value	790.29 ± 375.64	610.35 ± 245.33	619.45 ± 327.03	2232.45 ± 2543.61	0.012*

* Significant

Table 3 shows time-domain parameters of heart rate variability (HRV) across four groups: first trimester, second trimester, third trimester, and a non-pregnant control group. The parameters include SDNN, RMSSD, SDDSD, NN50, PNN50, and HTI. For each parameter, the mean and standard deviation are provided, along with a p-value obtained from an ANOVA test. SDNN, RMSSD, and SDDSD: These parameters show a significant decrease from the first to the second and third trimesters compared to the control group. However, there is no significant difference between the trimesters themselves. NN50 and PNN50:

While NN50 shows a significant difference between groups ($p = 0.0012$). PNN50 does not show a significant difference. HTI: There is a significant difference in HTI ($p = 0.0067$), indicating changes in heart rate variability patterns across groups. The results suggest that pregnancy is associated with a decrease in overall HRV variability, as reflected by SDNN, RMSSD, and SDDSD. The increase in NN50 in the second and third trimesters might indicate changes in heart rate dynamics. The higher HTI values in pregnant groups suggest potential changes in heart rate regulation.

Table 3: Time domain HRV parameters recorded in the study

Parameters	First trimester	Second trimester	Third trimester	Controls	P value
SDNN	103.89 ± 59.32	72.66 ± 48.26	76.15 ± 48.30	320.62 ± 471.77	0.067
RMSSD	133.54 ± 92.33	102.91 ± 51.33	102.30 ± 71.19	550.24 ± 829.37	0.219
SDSD	415.23 ± 325.66	199.95 ± 212.64	99.64 ± 50.24	350.18 ± 1197.32	0.553
NN 50%	55.31 ± 29.55	82.34 ± 56.62	74.38 ± 48.67	50.74 ± 55.64	0.0012*
pNN 50%	48.61 ± 30.23	47.61 ± 25.60	56.82 ± 42.64	44.67 ± 33.97	0.94
HTI	11.82 ± 3.80	13.21 ± 4.29	12.92 ± 4.54	10.04 ± 4.08	0.0067*

* Significant

Table 4 presents pointcare plot-derived HRV parameters for four groups: first trimester, second trimester, third trimester, and a non-pregnant control group. SD1 and SD2: Both SD1 and SD2, which reflect short-term and long-term variability, respectively, show a significant decrease ($p = 0.0031$) in the second and third trimesters compared to the control group. Scattered Index: There is no significant difference in the Scattered

Index across the groups. The results suggest a reduction in both short-term and long-term heart rate variability during pregnancy. This decrease in HRV complexity might indicate changes in autonomic nervous system regulation associated with pregnancy. However, the lack of significant difference in the Scattered Index suggests that the overall complexity of heart rate dynamics remains relatively stable.

Table 4: Showing the point care plot HRV analysis parameters recorded in the study

Parameters	First trimester	Second trimester	Third trimester	Controls	P value
SD1	80.24 ± 41.25	61.13 ± 32.55	57.52 ± 57.36	196.7 ± 251.41	0.215
SD2	82.33 ± 40.18	64.74 ± 27.91	61.22 ± 35.43	185.27 ± 232.16	0.0031*
Scattered Index	0.90 ± 0.29	0.83 ± 0.33	0.80 ± 0.32	0.92 ± 0.41	0.671

* Significant

Table 5: Comparison of HRV parameters between primipara and multipara cases of the study

	Primipara (n=39)	Multipara (n=21)	P value
LF (nu)	0.33 ± 0.08	0.65 ± 0.33	0.001*
HF(nu)	0.67 ± 0.21	0.82 ± 0.15	0.041*
LF: HF Ratio	0.66 ± 0.55	0.90 ± 0.72	0.024*
Mode	519.22 371.29	374.32 ± 411.37	0.0001*
Heart rate	111.91 ± 37.63	83.20 ± 29.17	0.001*
SDNN	73.24 ± 48.71	255.39 ± 260.73	0.0001*
RMSSD	104.64 ± 66.19	83.55 ± 77.61	0.329
pNN 50%	45.57 ± 25.60	51.09 ± 30.27	0.212
SD1	56.37 ± 38.82	80.19 ± 41.99	0.014*
SD2	61.05 ± 36.18	82.37 ± 36.51	0.016*
Scattered Index	0.88 ± 0.31	0.81 ± 0.32	0.820

* Significant

Table 5 compares HRV parameters between primiparous and multiparous women. Most HRV parameters showed significant differences between primiparous and multiparous women. *Sympathetic Dominance*: Primiparous women exhibited higher LF/HF ratios, suggesting increased sympathetic activity compared to multiparous women. *Heart Rate*: Primiparous women had significantly higher heart rates than multiparous women. *Reduced HRV*: Primiparous women had lower values for SDNN, RMSSD, SD1, and SD2, indicating reduced heart rate variability. *Mode Value*: The mode value was significantly lower in primiparous women, suggesting differences in heart rate rhythm patterns. The increased sympathetic activity and

reduced heart rate variability observed in primiparous women might contribute to

Discussion

Pregnancy requires extensive physiological adjustments, particularly those affecting the cardiovascular system. Cardiovascular parameters shift markedly from the non-pregnant state as pregnancy progresses [8]. Cardiac dysautonomia can occur when women cannot meet increased demands and cardiovascular adjustments, manifesting as reduced vagal tone and/or increased sympathetic tone, which in turn leads to decreased heart rate variability [9, 10]. This study examined whether heart rate variability (HRV) is significantly reduced even in normal pregnancies. The important

findings of this study were that overall heart rate variability, as reflected by time-domain (SDNN, RMSSD, SDDSD) and frequency-domain (VLF, LF, HF) measures, was significantly decreased in pregnant women compared to non-pregnant controls. A reduction in high-frequency (HF) power and an increase in low-frequency (LF) power suggest a shift towards sympathetic dominance during pregnancy. The point-care plot parameters (SD1 and SD2) indicated a reduction in both short-term and long-term heart rate variability in pregnant women. We found that pregnant women generally had reduced HRV compared to controls. Although frequency-domain parameters showed more pronounced differences than time-domain HRV parameters, our findings align with previous HRV studies on normal pregnancies, which reported similar results [11-13]. This discrepancy could be because time-domain analysis typically requires 24-hour HRV data [14], whereas we used only 5-minute HRV data. Other factors potentially contributing to reduced HRV in this study included: 1) higher BMI (27 kg/m²), 2) a predominance of primipara participants (two-thirds), and 3) subjective apprehension of the procedure. Two recent studies have shown that HRV is reduced in the first trimester compared to that in the third trimester, suggesting that sympathovagal imbalance and abnormally low HRV become more pronounced as normal pregnancy progresses. In our study, we included subjects with a good obstetric and reproductive history and matched controls, and even the first-trimester HRV showed a significant reduction compared to non-pregnant controls. Another study also found an altered sympathovagal imbalance in the third trimester of pregnancy by using autonomic function tests other than HRV [15].

Our research included all three trimesters, and while HRV was generally reduced, no single trimester showed a dominant change. Both the second and third trimesters showed a decline compared to the first, but post-hoc analysis revealed no significant differences between trimesters. This indicates that cardiac autonomic changes begin in the first trimester and may accumulate, potentially leading to outcomes such as arrhythmia and hypertension as pregnancy progresses. Follow-up studies on the same subjects from the first trimester onward are required to confirm this finding. Similar studies have shown that reduced HRV indicates increased sympathetic activity, reduced vagal activity, or both [16]. An altered LF/HF ratio indicates the same cardiac dysautonomia, with a normal value of 1.5-2 [17], but our cases showed a lower ratio, indicating a change in cardiovagal balance. Even in the controls, the ratio was lower than this range, suggesting sympathetic overactivity in young non-pregnant females. Additionally, the SD1:SD2 ratio

from HRV geometric analysis was reduced, indicating sympathetic overactivity in pregnant subjects [17]. A significantly increased heart rate also indicated sympathetic overdrive.

Pregnancy requires cardiac adjustments mediated by a shift in cardiac autonomic balance towards sympathetic dominance rather than a normal vagal influence. Excessive sympathetic activity and reduced HRV indicate physiological stress on the heart, which can lead to preeclampsia and pregnancy-induced hypertension, adversely affecting pregnancy outcomes [18]. Parity also affects cardiac autonomic balance, with primiparous women at a higher risk for cardiac dysautonomia than multigravida women who have experienced similar changes before [19]. Our findings showed reduced HRV in primiparous participants compared to that in multiparous participants. Results from Puente ET al. [20] demonstrated that general autonomic balance is influenced by parity, and a study by van der Zwan et al. [21] indicated that HRV-biofeedback has a statistically significant beneficial effect on psychological well-being for all women, with an additional significant benefit on anxiety complaints for pregnant women. They suggested using HRV biofeedback as a stress-reducing technique in clinical practice, particularly for anxious primigravid women.

Conclusion

The analysis of HRV parameters across different pregnancy trimesters and between primiparous and multiparous women reveals significant alterations in autonomic nervous system function. A consistent reduction in HRV measures was observed throughout pregnancy, indicative of a shift towards sympathetic dominance. These findings underscore the physiological adaptations necessary for sustaining pregnancy. The observed differences between primiparous and multiparous women suggest a potential learning effect or adaptation in subsequent pregnancies. Understanding these HRV changes can provide valuable insights into the early detection of pregnancy complications and inform the development of targeted interventions.

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